

THE FUNCTION OF PROTEINS IN THE BODY OF ANIMALS

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ANNOTATION

Proteins are the most important component of a living organism. Proteins make up about 16-18% of the body's live weight and are constantly kept in dynamic balance. Proteins include carbon, hydrogen, and oxygen, as well as nitrogen, sulfur, and in some cases phosphorus. The most common proteins, albumin and globulin, contain an average of 54% carbon, 7% hydrogen, 16% nitrogen, 1% sulfur, and 0.22% oxygen. The shapes of different protein molecules are the same - elongated, spherical and other shapes.

Keywords: Protein, hydrogen, tissue, nitrogen, organism.

Along with nutrients, proteins must constantly enter the body from the outside. The body does not synthesize proteins from fats and carbohydrates. This is because nitrogen, which is present in proteins, is not found in fats and carbohydrates. the amount of protein in the body, as mentioned above, is maintained at a relatively certain standard. However, although the amount of tissue proteins is relatively certain, they are constantly changing, exchanging, and renewing. This is because proteins are broken down and re-synthesized according to the body's needs. Proteins are mainly plastic and partly energetic in the body. The plasticity of proteins is due to the fact that they are important components of cells. The energy value is determined by the amount of energy released when they break down and used by the organism for life. The amino acids formed after digestion of proteins entering the body with nutrients are broken down by a number of enzymes in the digestive tract. A small amount of protein is absorbed in the stomach. It is believed that a small amount of protein is absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract in the form of short peptides, without being broken down into amino acids. There is evidence

that in the gastrointestinal tract of young, newborn animals, some proteins can be absorbed directly without being broken down. Amino acids and other protein products absorbed into the blood are delivered to the liver through the portal vein, where some of the body's own proteins are synthesized. The rest of the amino acids are transported by the blood to all the cells and tissues of the body, where specific proteins are synthesized in the ribosomes, nuclei and mitochondria of the cells. The formation, re-synthesis, and renewal of proteins in different parts of the body is uneven. In particular, it was mentioned above that almost half of the cell proteins in the liver are regenerated in 3-5 days. Proteins in the blood plasma are also regenerated much faster. By injecting methionine, which contains radioactive sulfur, A.V. Palladin proved that proteins in the central nervous system are exchanged faster than the cerebral hemispheres and the gray matter of the brain. Amino acids that are not involved in the synthesis of tissue proteins are deaminated and converted to keto acids in the liver and kidneys by the loss of the amino group (NH_2). In the liver, the amino group produces ammonia, which is used to make urea. Urea is excreted through the kidneys. In 1895, P. Pavlov et al. Proved that urea is actually formed in the liver. When the portal vein of the liver is connected to the next vena cava (ECK-Pavlov method), the amount of urea excreted in the urine decreases sharply, and ammonia accumulates in the blood in the form of ammonium salts. As a result, the body becomes severely poisoned. This experiment completely confirms the formation of urea from ammonia in the liver. In addition, the fact that ammonia in the blood of the capillary vein is about three times higher than in the blood of the hepatic vein also indicates the formation of urea from ammonia in the liver. The conversion of ammonia into urea or other waste substances (urine, acid, allantoin) is extremely important for the body. Because these substances made from ammonia are relatively harmless to the body than ammonia. It has recently become clear that small amounts of ammonia produced in the body can be detoxified without being converted to urea or other substances. For example, all tissues in the body always contain a certain amount of glutamic acid. It can bind a small amount of ammonia to form a more non-toxic compound,

glutamine. In addition, asparagine acid in muscles can perform a similar function. There is evidence that tissue proteins can also attach to themselves and form non-toxic compounds when needed. The ammonia contained in these compounds is then excreted from the body in the form of urea or uric acid. Fatty acids are formed from keto acids formed after the deamination of proteins. When the fatty acids formed are more complex, they are converted to acetic acid by the beta oxidation reaction, and more simply, they are directly involved in carbohydrate metabolism and are broken down into water and carbon dioxide. Thus, a certain amount of energy is released as a result of these reactions. Thus, keto acids serve as a source of energy in the body. In the body, amino acids undergo deamination and decarboxylation, which means that they lose their carboxyl group. As a result, various amino acids are formed. Some amines are toxic, but in a normal organism amines are converted into aldehydes by appropriate enzymes, which are involved in carbohydrate metabolism in the body and are broken down into water and carbon dioxide. It is also involved in the synthesis of amino acids, vitamins, hormones, enzymes, pigments. For example, from the tyrosine the adrenal gland is necessary for the synthesis of the hormones adrenaline, the thyroid gland thyroxine, the triiodothyronine, and the skin produces the pigment melanin. Lysine produces calamine and choline, which are needed to synthesize phosphatides. Certain amino acids are necessary for the body to produce certain physiological functions. For example, tryptophan, tyrosine, arginine, and sulfur-containing amino acids are important for the growth of a young organism. The amino acid cystine is important in the growth of wool, horns, hooves, feathers, feathers, the nervous system, tryptophan in the reproductive organs, and leucine in the synthesis of plasma proteins. This means that some amino acids are important for the body. The number of known amino acids now stands at 25. Not all of these amino acids are always present in the proteins that enter the body with food. However, some amino acids in the body are converted to others by re-amino acids to form new amino acids. It was first discovered in 1937 by A.E. Braunstein and M.G. Krisman. It is now known that all known amino acids are involved in the process of re-assimilation. However,

not all of the essential amino acids for the body's life are synthesized in the body. In particular, there are a number of amino acids that, without being synthesized in the body, must enter the body from the outside in the form of proteins, along with the food that is consumed. Such amino acids that are not synthesized in the body are called irreplaceable amino acids. These include tryptophan, lysine, threonine, phenylalanine, methionine, leucine, isoleucine, arginine, histidine, and valin. These include an organism shuva volin. If an organism is deprived of one of these amino acids, protein synthesis is disrupted, resulting in the body; In particular, the animal stops growing. It cannot live long without breaking its normal state. Proteins that are irreplaceable and retain all of their amino acids are called complete proteins. If a protein does not contain one or more of the essential amino acids, it is called a complete protein. Normal growth and development of the body does not maintain all the essential amino acids in the proteins consumed for the normal functioning of life processes. Therefore, in order to meet the body's need for all amino acids, the nutrients it needs must be varied. In this case, the amino acid content of the second protein can be replaced by the amino acid content of the second protein. Satisfies and becomes completely valuable for the organism. Therefore, the animal's diet; The amino acid content of the feed should be pre-tested, in particular the ration should be designed to replace the amino acid deficiency in one feed with the amino acid content in the other. The value of protein also depends on the type of digestive process in the animal. For example, due to the microbiological processes that take place in the large intestine of a four-chambered complex chewing gum, proteins that are not completely valuable to other animals may become completely valuable to them. The fact is that the microorganisms in the large intestine synthesize the proteins of their bodies from nutrient proteins and non-protein nitrogenous substances. The amount of amino acids in the diet is also taken into account in order to create favorable conditions for the good synthesis of proteins in the animal's body. For example, corn protein is a completely invaluable protein, meaning that it cannot survive, grow, and develop on its own. Also, less than 8-9% of lactalbumin in the diet does not meet the body's need for these protein amino acids.

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